

1 The performance of Mediterranean low-income 2 housing in scenarios involving climate change.

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8 Abstract

9 Social housing dating from the period between the Second World War and the end of the oil
10 crisis is one of the major stores of residential stock of European cities. This housing stock is a
11 major target for retrofitting given its characteristic poor thermal performance and inefficient
12 control of energy consumption. This article proposes a method for analysing the dynamic
13 capacity of thermal enclosures on moderate energy flows in building stock in climate change
14 scenarios, estimating the potential for adaptation and strengths and weaknesses of several
15 building categories exposed to different present and future climate scenarios. A pilot study
16 applying the procedure is carried out in the city of Seville, one of the largest in southern Europe,
17 with a representative northern Mediterranean climate. The approach designed is equally
18 applicable to other urban centres in southern Europe. Although indoor comfort in cold weather
19 must be addressed even in the least favourable future scenarios, the predominant concern for
20 this stock is controlling heat gain. This study shows how, regardless of individual situations,
21 thermal insulation alone does not guarantee an optimal response for the stock as a whole.
22 Different categories can be identified within a given stock, where some buildings display
23 significant resilience and potential for adaptation to new scenarios, while others have less scope
24 for improvement. These conclusions can provide guidelines for the design of future intervention
25 policies in southern Europe.

26 **Keywords:** social housing; climatic change; southern Europe; energy demand; monitoring;
27 simulation.

28 1. Introduction

29 Social housing, in its collective building form, is central to the configuration of current cities in
30 southern Europe. The considerable volume of housing built in Europe after World War II [1], [2]
31 and in Spain after the Civil War greatly affects the current energy behaviour of urban housing,
32 and must be taken into account when assessing the energy performance expected from these
33 cities. In Seville over 48 % of multi-family residential buildings - the most common type - were
34 built between 1939 and 1979 [3], [4]. Together with the buildings constructed in the early
35 twentieth century, this figure adds up to over 51 % of present housing stock. Consequently, over
36 half of the city's homes are to some extent obsolete. Of this 51%, 60% qualifies as 'social housing'

37 and accounts for over 30 % of Seville's total housing stock, which is at serious risk of
38 underperformance. As a result, social housing and its capacity to continue to accommodate a
39 large part of the population when faced with future changes is called into question, given the
40 effects of climate change on consumption and indoor comfort conditions.

41 Social housing is usually occupied by medium to low-income families with limited resources to
42 invest in the control of the indoor environment. These conditions lead to situations affecting the
43 health, comfort, and quality of life of residents and should not be approached from the
44 standpoint of energy consumption alone. These factors must therefore all be taken into
45 consideration both when designing global policies to improve the performance of building stock
46 in general and when planning specific interventions.

47 Given current energy and emissions requirements [5] [6] and the sub-standard habitability
48 deriving from shortcomings in the building stock [7], suitable solutions are needed to lower
49 energy demands - and in turn energy consumption - in order to substantially improve indoor
50 environmental conditions. The most pressing concerns are the envelopes, particularly the
51 façades of multi-family buildings [8], given their crucial importance in ensuring the quality of
52 the indoor environment (thermal, acoustic control and air quality), and building aesthetics in
53 terms of the image of the city [9].

54 This research aims primarily to present a wide-ranging study on the energy performance of
55 social housing in the city of Seville, one of the largest in Spain, with a characteristic climate highly
56 representative of southern Europe [10]–[12]. In cities with mild winters and warm summers
57 (even extreme ones), indoor thermal conditions, particularly in social housing, are usually
58 conditioned by economic considerations as well as a widespread lack of cooling and heating
59 systems in homes and poor building performance [7]. This analysis aims to establish probable
60 bands for the potential modification of the energy behaviour of building stock, rather than to
61 establish specific values for buildings which should be the subject of specific studies.

62 One of the main innovations of this study, in the context of urban buildings, is that local weather
63 is constantly changing, both through its natural variability and the effect of anthropogenic
64 factors such as the different processes of climate change (CC). The climate which affects
65 buildings has undergone – and will continue to undergo – changes which will have a direct effect
66 on buildings' energy performance [13], [14] and comfort [15], [16]. The characteristics of this
67 evolution and the main interactions with these buildings are analysed, generating a future
68 evaluation scenario in order to establish a correlation between current and potential future
69 scenarios in terms of factors driving building energy performance and energy use in indoor
70 climate control.

71 Although this analysis focuses on the evolution of housing stock in the city of Seville, the work
72 methodology and classification procedures followed are equally applicable to other cities and
73 urban areas in southern Europe.

74 As mentioned above, current environmental conditions, coupled with the effects of climate
75 change, affect energy balances. This is especially noticeable among social groups of lower
76 economic status, often affected by increased demands on energy supply systems for the

77 improvement of indoor conditions [17]. As the energy demand for the thermal control of the
78 buildings is directly related to climatic conditions, modifying these will lead to new energy
79 scenarios for cities and urban areas [14], [17]–[19].

80 Retrofitting actions to reduce CO₂ emissions from residential buildings and enhance energy
81 savings are usually evaluated considering the conditions of the current climate (and on occasion
82 historical data). This is particularly useful when establishing the performance of present-day
83 buildings in future climate conditions, as well as the potential performance of the energy
84 improvement measures currently under development for residential buildings, and their
85 effectiveness in a future iteration of the current climate. This issue is examined by Hooff [20],
86 Gupta [21] and Roders [22] although focusing fundamentally on colder areas in Europe.

87 A comprehensive review of the literature on the impact of climate change on building
88 performance can be found in [23]–[25] for the fundamental concepts and methods and a global
89 review in [26]–[29], covering the most recent trends. In general, it is emphasized that in
90 predominantly warm conditions or in areas with a balance between heating and cooling needs,
91 the potential for reduction of energy (or emissions) is strongly altered by the effects of climate
92 change [23] [30]. In the Mediterranean area, the increase in the cooling needs of homes,
93 especially those of lower constructive quality, is especially significant, as in [31] for Greece,
94 where a significant increase in cooling degree days and maximum indoor temperatures
95 (naturally ventilated homes) is forecast.

96 **2. Methodology**

97 This paper proposes a method for the analysis at housing stock-scale of the dynamic and
98 evolutive capacity of the thermal envelopes trading energy flows within climate change
99 scenarios. A probability assessment has been developed to establish the performance expected
100 for city housing stock by 2050. This short to medium timeline will provide the key points for
101 effective and economic actions in cities, calculating the potential for adaptation as well as the
102 strengths and weaknesses of various building categories when exposed to different present and
103 future climate scenarios.

104 In order to evaluate the potential impact of a climate change scenario on a multi-family social
105 housing block in southern Spain, this study simulates a representative sample for housing units
106 from the current social housing stock in 6 different scenarios. For the first scenario complying

107 with the current demand stipulations of Spanish CTE-DB-HE1 regulation [32] an alternative
108 scenario is introduced to provide a realistic assessment of the current energy use in the
109 dwellings, and the same model is subsequently used to evaluate energy variables for climate
110 conditions predicted for the year 2050.

111 This study is made up of the phases of:

- 112 – characterisation of social housing
- 113 – selection of case studies
- 114 – monitoring

- 115 – climate model development
- 116 – simulations under six scenarios.

117 **2.1. Characterisation of social housing**

118 Given the lack of a database for social housing in Seville, this study required an exhaustive data
119 collection process to identify the developments built between 1939 and 1979. A thorough
120 review was carried out of original documents in national, regional and local historic and
121 government archives, as well as in the records of engineering firms. Documentary analysis was
122 followed by the on-site inspection of several buildings for the comparison of as-built and
123 planned or design data, identifying any changes made since their construction.

124 The information and documentation compiled was entered into a database with historic,
125 geometric and technical data in numerical and graph formats. This information was
126 supplemented with new drawings and the inspection of construction systems. The data
127 compiled and the specific characterisation is developed in [9] for performance and construction
128 characteristics of envelopes and in [33] where the cataloguing process and data set is discussed.
129 This database features information from 99,437 social dwellings built in the period under study.

130 **2.2. Selection of case studies**

131 The buildings studied were selected after a comprehensive process to faithfully represent the
132 building stock. The first phase consisted of the identification and characterisation of the social
133 housing developments built within the city limits in the period studied (1940-1979), 250
134 developments totalling 99,437 dwellings of an expected total of 100,510 were identified, and
135 those which were especially small or far too unique to have representation in the stock were
136 discarded [4]: in other words 98.93 %, which for all practical purposes can be considered as
137 the entire population. Exhaustive data collection was carried out, identifying affordable and social-
138 type housing units in the city, including location, typological characterisation and the cataloguing of
139 units. National, regional and local archives from historical, governmental and technical organisations
140 were consulted in the data collection process, while information and documentation from press,
141 technical journals from the period studied and a scientific literature review were also analysed. Further
142 fieldwork was carried out to inspect buildings on site, collecting data for the comparison of construction
143 plans and existing buildings, allowing further evolution and transformations experienced since their
144 construction to be identified. This procedure has resulted in an extensive database of historical and
145 descriptive data: geometric, typological and constructive parameters and other technical aspects, both
146 numerical and graphical. Data set and catalogue details are included in [33]

147 Analysis led to the identification of the characteristics common to each time frame (walls, roofs
148 and other constructive element types, size of dwellings, windows and wall areas, etc.), with
149 decades selected as sub-periods to guarantee an improved practical approach. A sample group
150 of the stock (covering 83 developments and 46,476 units or 47 % of the population) was used
151 to establish the essential morpho-constructive features of these developments [9], represented
152 by the buildings selected (Tables 1 and 2, Figure 1). This group was selected for Stratified
153 sampling and used to analyse energy demand performance in the different present and future
154 climate scenarios. This group includes a representation (typical buildings) of each decade based

155 on the differences revealed between time periods in earlier analysis, and mostly resulting from
 156 the implementation of housing construction programmes and ordinances [9]. Sampling
 157 precision was improved through stratification with variable strata sizes [34]. The sample size of
 158 each stratum was adapted depending on standard deviation to ensure the minimum variance in
 159 the mean of the sample [35]. This resulted in a sample covering 14 developments (13,898
 160 housing units in total) with a sampling fraction (f_h) of 0.056. The buildings were defined using
 161 non-probabilistic, directed selection, making up a modelling sample for exploratory research
 162 design built using the ‘typical cases’ method [36]. The data sourced from an earlier study (matrix)
 163 included quotas to ensure that all the usual types present in each sub-period were represented
 164 and that clear in-depth information was provided on the performance of these characteristic
 165 types. The development component was used as it was considered the minimum grouping for
 166 multi-family buildings within the housing stock. When the number of units is used as a
 167 parameter it does not allow suitable discrimination, given that it is a discrete variable (units are
 168 grouped in buildings forming part of developments). Nonetheless, for the fit resulting from
 169 applying an f_h factor = 0.138, the approximation is suitable and compatible with the
 170 developments selected and assignment error is therefore minimised. The major geometrical
 171 envelope parameters are given in Table 1, while a comprehensive data analysis of the stock can
 172 be found in [33].

173 Table 1: Sample selected for energy modelling: main quantitative parameters

Model	Building				Development					
	Year	Decade	ND	S _F	S _w	S _R	ND	S _F	S _w	S _R
A	1952	50	20	878	171	273	1,180	51,802	10,061	16,107
B	1955	50	60	5,672	1,387	689	300	28,358	6,933	3,445
C	1959	50	8	248	44	89	1,611	49,975	8,848	17,922
D	1961	60	8	309	66	115	1,013	39,107	8,302	14,562
E	1963	60	20	1,009	157	324	554	27,940	4,347	8,975
F	1964	60	8	322	65	138	1,680	67,620	13,650	28,980
G	1964	60	30	2,071	252	358	300	20,712	2,520	3,580
H	1966	60	20	822	290	230	840	34,524	12,180	9,660
I	1971	70	24	1,520	242	470	2,768	178,164	28,365	55,090
J	1974	70	45	2,480	511	330	540	29,765	6,132	3,960
K	1976	70	40	5,302	866	710	640	84,832	13,856	11,354
L	1977	70	8	329	56	149	1,048	42,954	7,311	19,453
M	1979	70	32	2,603	304	359	800	65,075	7,600	8,975
N	1979	70	16	1,106	162	378	624	43,134	6,318	14,723
			(dwellings)	(sqm)			(dwellings)	(sqm)		

174 This analysis aims to establish distributions and patterns to define and classify the actions based
 175 on:

- 176 - Patterns and aggregation by time period of developments.
- 177 - Aggregation by basic magnitude: construction type and general dimensions.

- 178 - Morphological parameters related to energy performances of the building
179 envelope: wall or roof surfaces, wall to window ratio or wall to indoor area,
180 compactness and other parameters.
181 - Construction systems and temporary distribution.

182 The energy and morphological parameters for the models are listed in Table 2. Developments
183 with the lowest % of openings on the façade (approximately 12 %) are models M and G. The
184 models with the highest percentage of openings on the façade are B and H (24% and 35 %
185 respectively). Models A, D and E are composed of single-brick façades. The housing units of
186 models M and N are representative of developments with thermal insulation in the envelope,
187 both on the roof and the façade. The 1970s saw an increase in the number of sloping roofs in
188 multi-family housing (models I, M and N).

189 Table 2. Energy and morphological parameters

Model		Morphological parameters (m ²)				Energy parameters (W/m ² K)		
Model	Year	ND	S _F	S _W	S _R	U _F	U _R	U _G
A	1952	20	878	171	273	1.83	2.40	2.45
B	1955	60	5 672	1 387	689	1.53	1.23	2.25
C	1959	8	248	44	89	1.28	1.23	1.66
D	1961	8	309	66	115	1.83	1.23	2.07
E	1963	20	1 009	157	324	1.97	1.57	2.17
F	1964	8	322	65	138	1.28	1.23	1.81
G	1964	30	2 071	252	358	1.68	1.57	2.04
H	1966	20	822	290	230	1.53	1.23	1.91
I	1971	24	1 520	242	470	2.17	2.40	2.49
J	1974	45	2 480	511	330	1.53	1.84	2.20
K	1976	40	5 302	866	710	1.53	1.23	2.06
L	1977	8	329	56	149	1.53	1.54	1.97
M	1979	32	2 603	304	359	0.72	0.67	1.18
N	1979	16	1 106	162	378	0.75	0.67	1.22

190

191 Where:

- 192 - S_F Area of opaque façade (m²)
193 - S_W Window area (m²)
194 - S_R Roof area (m²)
195 - ND No. of dwelling
196 - U_F Thermal transmittance, opaque façade enclosure (W/m²K)
197 - U_R Thermal transmittance, roof (W/m²K)
198 - U_G Thermal transmittance, building as a whole (W/m²K)

199 In Seville, the smaller housing units associated with social programmes for population with
200 limited means, have mostly been built in medium-height or tall buildings (models A, C, D, E, F,
201 H, I, L, N). The housing units in taller tower blocks, approximately 27 % of the total (models B, G,

202 J, K), have larger surfaces than medium-height buildings. There is also a correlation between the
203 size of the housing unit and the block type, as housing units tend to be smaller in linear than in
204 H-type blocks [9].

205

Figure 1: Building energy modelling by main time period (DesignBuilder).

207 **2.3. Actual performance data gathering**

208 One of the main aims of this study is to identify the difference between real use patterns and
 209 those proposed by the National Standards [10] (Table 3) . The actual intensity of use and
 210 conditions within the buildings tend to differ, leading to a distortion when evaluating demand.
 211 This is reflected mostly in the variations in energy flow due to the different indoor temperatures.
 212 In some cases, a monitoring process was carried out to identify the most frequent indoor
 213 temperatures, and in turn, to establish new comparison scenarios. Indoor environmental
 214 parameters (temperature, relative humidity and CO₂ levels) were monitored continuously for a
 215 full year in the selected housing units using a Wöhler CDL 210 multi-parametric monitoring
 216 system (one control -housing unit in each development). Outdoor humidity, temperature, and
 217 wind velocity were provided by the Spanish meteorological agency (AEMET). These
 218 measurements were used to establish a pattern of use closer to that normally expected in this
 219 type of housing unit rather than the standard patterns defined by national regulation for energy-
 220 demand compliance simulations. The starting conditions for the construction of the models are
 221 based on the operational patterns established by the Spanish Standards for energy in buildings:
 222 the National Energy Labelling procedure [37] and the national requirement for energy
 223 conservation (CTE DB-HE) [38], regulations which implement the European Energy Performance
 224 Building Directive (EPBD) at national level [39]. (Table 3):

225 Table 3. Heating/AC temperature set-point schedule as in Spanish national Standards [37] [38].

Target temperature (°C)	1:00- 7:00	8:00	9:00- 15:00	16:00- 23:00	24:00
January to May (lowest)	17	20	20	20	17
June to September (highest)	27	free running	free running	25	27
October to December (lowest)	17	20	20	20	17

226 *free running = mechanical thermal control off

227 This operational definition can be defined as the Normative Scenario. It should be noted that this
 228 pattern assumes an almost continuous use of heating in winter, which is not the usual situation
 229 in social housing stock [40], [41]. For the purposes of comparison assessment, an alternative and
 230 complementary scenario was proposed as part of the discussion of the results from the
 231 environmental variables and the analysis of user surveys monitored (Table 4), and is developed
 232 in [10].

233 This scenario is introduced to provide a more consistent model for the actual energy-use of
 234 housing (especially in social housing), occupational profile, and heating and air conditioning
 235 operation. The statistical development for the definition of the schedule and the analysis of the
 236 indoor environmental data are covered in [10].

237

238 Table 4. Alternative Heating/AC temperature set-point schedule for social housing.

Target temperature (°C)	1:00- 7:00	8:00	9:00- 15:00	16:00- 23:00	24:00
January to May (lowest)	15	19	19	19	15
June to September (highest)	free running	free running	free running	27	free running
October to December (lowest)	15	19	19	19	15

239 *free running = mechanical thermal control off

240 In general, it can be established that the use of normative scenarios in the energy assessment
 241 of the housing units results in an overestimation of the energy linked to the thermal exchanges
 242 in these buildings. This especially affects the effect of energy-conservation measures (such as
 243 retrofitting insulation), increasing the weight of the energy contribution in cold periods.
 244 The envelope airtightness of the housing units was measured using the standard blower door
 245 test (as defined by EN 13829:2000 [42]) and a complementary methodology developed for this
 246 type of multifamily buildings, which define specific techniques for measuring the contribution
 247 of the components of the dwellings to air-infiltration through five additional tests where the
 248 sequential increase in sealing elements makes it possible to allocate infiltration responsibility
 249 for the envelope [43]. The ‘Minneapolis Blower Door Model 4’ kit used was connected to an
 250 automated performance testing system (flow range at 50 Pa, 25–7800 m³ h⁻¹; accuracy, ±
 251 3%). Measurements were taken at pressures ranging from 20 Pa to 70 Pa at 5 Pa intervals
 252 following the procedures described in Spanish and European standard UNE EN 13829:2002 [44].
 253 Mean value for the stock is 7.51 h⁻¹ (+/- 2.74 h⁻¹ STD). Broad results were published in [11], [43],
 254 [45].

255 Indoor and outdoor environmental parameters and airtightness were also used to calibrate the
 256 energy demand simulation model.

257 **2.4. Climate model development**

258 Therefore, the use of dynamic simulation techniques for energy behaviour on meteorological
 259 predictions will be necessary in order to evaluate the impact of climate change on buildings and
 260 their indoor ambient. These techniques must establish a representative dataset for the future
 261 conditions which these buildings must face. The use of meteorological data with at least hourly
 262 details - and representative of the future scenarios for evaluation - is necessary to ensure precise
 263 dynamic analysis of thermal and energy responses of buildings [46].

264 The climate fluctuations in the city of Seville for the period between the construction of this
 265 housing stock and the present were studied to understand the changes undergone by these
 266 buildings to date and to establish the base-line for the climate evolution trend. The second step
 267 was the development of a ‘typical year’ weather-data set for a future period under the evolution
 268 driven by climate change processes. This procedure was borrowed from Jentsch et al. [47] from

269 the University of Southampton's Sustainable Energy Research Group: a methodology and
270 process algorithms to develop future standard weather years, factoring in the effects of climate
271 change. This procedure draws from the morphing methodology established by Belcher et al.
272 [48]. and the work by Chan et al. [46] for the development of hourly weather files. This
273 approach drives the transformation of current local daily data, a mathematical transformation
274 referred to as morphing [47], through regional (RCM, Regional Climate Models) or global (GCM,
275 Global Climate Models) climate change forecast models. This ensures a set of future local data
276 with hourly information. In this research the EPW (Energy Plus Weather) format was selected to
277 represent typical yearly weather, where the data for Seville were adapted from the SWE
278 (Spanish Weather for Energy Calculations) type-year. A displacement and stretch calculation
279 technique was applied, imposing the foreseeable modifications derived from global models to
280 current data [47]. This probabilistic approach introduces climate variability and uncertainty
281 factors, allowing the adaptation of present weather data to new conditions [49]. This method is
282 one of the most commonly used for future performance simulations, especially within the
283 United Kingdom where it has been adopted by CIBSE [50] and validated by [30].

284 The difference with other probabilistic methods is the reduction of scenarios in comparison with
285 other more extensive ones, such as that developed for the program UKCP09 [51], which
286 generates 100 sequences of 30 years. Although this method allows very detailed probability
287 distributions to be established, the vast amount of data generated makes it unsuitable for work
288 with building stocks [47]. Equally, although models based on RCM (Regional Climatic Models)
289 are preferable for the generation of regional scenarios, given their higher geographical
290 resolution [52], they are less efficient as driving forces for current weather morphing
291 procedures as they have fewer consistent parameters [53]. The use of GCM (Global Climatic
292 Models) for data transformation is considered a suitable estimation, especially for the periods
293 close in time and for the assessment of building performance [47]. The dataset generated by
294 [54] for Europe, includes five climate models (CGCM2, CSIRO-Mk2, ECHAM4, HadCM3,
295 NCARPCM) and four emission scenarios (B1, B2, A2, A1FI) [55] [56]. Although this method may
296 have limitations when working with time-extended scenarios such as those through to 2080,
297 [47] it is not a conditioning factor for this work given its focus. In practical terms it does not seem
298 useful to extend the analysis beyond the middle of the century as the assessment of the energy
299 potential of the current housing stock beyond this time would provide no additional information,
300 as the level of renewal of the current stock beyond this period of reference is expected to be
301 very high as well as the uncertainty of the climate forecasts. The HadCM3 (Hadley Centre
302 Coupled Model, version 3) model [57], [58] was selected as it presents the higher number of
303 parameters to feed the morphing process suitably. Scenario A2, representing the most probable
304 unfavourable scenario, was selected to develop future weather models. It can be assumed that
305 this represents the expected evolution of our current society without major changes and can
306 therefore be adopted as the upper threshold for change in relation to the current situation
307 (some scenarios have greater impact but are highly improbable)

308 Climate change data from general climatic models, in this case monthly predictions from
309 HAdRM3 type models [15], are regionalised ('spatial downscaling') with the application of the
310 starting conditions referring to the city location (data included in the typical meteorological year
311 for the city—in this case EPW). This type of model has been shown to be meteorologically

312 consistent [48]. The city- future weather profiles developed for the years 2020 and 2050
313 (HadCM3-A2 scenario) are represented with monthly average values against the current
314 weather for Seville (EPW format) as accepted for regulatory energy simulations (Figure 2).

315

316 Figure 2: Comparison of average monthly air temperatures ($^{\circ}$ C) and annual average for the
317 current meteorological year (EPW), and models showing evolution for 2020 and 2050.

318 2.5. Energy modelling

319 The building sample-group is modelled to recreate geometric, morphological and typological
320 characteristics, construction systems, urban environment and operational conditions. The
321 models include urban boundary conditions and solar horizon surroundings (Figure 1).

322 The building energy simulation tool EnergyPlus v8.2 was chosen for this purpose, through the
323 energy analysis package DesignBuilder (v4.2.0.054), whose validity can be considered
324 adequately proven [59] [60]. The building modelling of simulation sets followed the
325 methodology detailed in ANSI/ASHRAE/IES Standard 90.1-2013 [61], with initial operational
326 protocols established according to Spanish official Energy Labelling procedures and adapted to
327 a more realistic approach in the second step.

328 A calibration procedure was then carried out between models and real housing units to check
329 the accuracy of the model compared to actual performance. Control homes were used both as
330 a source for the identification of thermal behaviour and for the calibration of the nodal model.
331 Thermal and operational real profiles for calibration were created by extracting hourly values
332 for indoor parameters as in [62] and using real weather data to feed the climate file. the mean
333 bias error (MBE) and the coefficient of variation of the root mean square error (CV/RMSE) (3)
334 were used to assess the differences between the simulated and hourly data observed.

335
$$MBE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} y_i} \quad (1)$$

336
$$\hat{Y}_S = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} y_i}{N_s} \quad (2)$$

337
$$CVRMSE_{(S)} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{N_s}}}{\hat{Y}_S} \quad (3)$$

338 where:

- 339 - y_i : recorded data
340 - \hat{y}_i : simulated data
341 - N_s : sample size
342 - \hat{Y}_S : sample mean for recorded data

343 Different parameters were adjusted to reach convergence (airtightness, material density and
344 thermal resistance, floor temperature...) through a GOF (*Goodness-Of-Fit*) method as explained
345 by Coakley et al. where for each model it is based on a weighted combination of CVRMSE and
346 the NMBE, comparing the simulation models with lower results they represent parameter sets
347 showing a higher goodness of fit in relation to the measured data, thus allowing the selection of
348 better fits [63]. The calibration process was conducted following ASHRAE 14-2002, establishing
349 that the simulation model calibrated must have 10% accuracy range for NBME and 30% for CV
350 (RMSE) in relation to the hourly data measured [64].

351 Figure 3 shows an example of calibration process output for models E and H (Figure 1) during
352 one winter week. Figure 3 shows actual indoor temperature with measurement error (± 0.5 °C)
353 in contrast with simulated indoor temperature. In both examples, MBE and CV/RMSE values
354 were well within the limits established in ASHRAE 14-2002 (E: 0.54/6.69% and 0.93/11.48%;
355 H:1.94/23.88 and 1.68/20.62%).

356

357

358 *Figure 3: Comparison of observed and simulated indoor air temperatures (°C) for models E and*
 359 *H using outdoor air temperature (°C) as a reference for a summer reference week.*

360 **2.6. Assessment scenarios**

361 The different analysis scenarios used are derived from the combination of the different states:
 362 current standard (national regulation) and alternative low energy intensity scenario; basic
 363 envelope and envelope retrofitting (insulation); current climate and future weather.

364 Table 5 shows the state-combinations to draw up the different scenarios where six are chosen
 365 to develop the comparative assessment. They are used in the simulations where 339 dwellings
 366 grouped into 14 different buildings (Table 1) are simulated for each scenario

367 Table 5. Scenarios used in simulations.

Scenario		OA	OB	RA	RB	FOB	FRB
Envelope	Original	X	X			X	
	Retrofitted			X	X		X
Climate	Present	X	X	X	X		
	Future					X	X
Temperature set	CTE	X		X			
	Alternative		X		X	X	X

368

369 Where:

- 370 - OA original building and Spanish standard set temperature
- 371 - OB original building and alternative set temperature
- 372 - RA retrofitted building and Spanish standard set temperature
- 373 - RB retrofitted building and alternative set temperature
- 374 - FOB future climate, original building and alternative set temperature
- 375 - FRB future climate, retrofitted building and alternative set temperature

376

377 Operational schedules, shown in Table 6, are based on those from the national EPDB
378 implementation procedures, with percentages representing the partial application of the
379 schedule during this time frame [65].

380 *Table 6: Dwelling Operational Profiles*

Activity	Value	Schedule			
		Winter		Summer	
Occupation	0.056 pers/m ²	00:00 to 07:00	100%	00:00 to 07:00	100%
		07:00 to 16:00	25%	07:00 to 16:00	25%
		16:00 to 23:00	50%	16:00 to 23:00	50%
		Weekends & holidays:		Weekends 00:00 to 24:00	100
		00:00 to 24:00	50%	Holidays 00:00 to 24:00	0%
Equipment & Lighting	0.44 W/m ²	00:00 to 08:00	10%	00:00 to 08:00	10%
		08:00 to 19:00	30%	08:00 to 19:00	30%
		19:00 to 20:00	50%	19:00 to 20:00	50%
		20:00 to 23:00	100%	20:00 to 23:00	100%
		23:00 to 24:00	50%	23:00 to 24:00	50%
Supplementary ventilation	3 ACH	<i>not applicable</i>		00:00 to 08:00	100%
				08:00 to 24:00	0%

Winter: from November to March
Summer: from April to October

381

382 **2.6.1. Envelope**

383 Constructions were considered to be as originally built, an assumption compatible with the
384 normal state of affairs since most of the past interventions on façades of the stock were only
385 repairs. Windows are considered second-generation upgrades, with steel frames and single
386 glazing, and with little to no thermal effect compared to the original windows [9].

387 In the retrofitted stage the façade was assumed to have been improved by the external addition
388 of an insulation layer, a 5 cm *External Thermal Insulation Composite System* (ETICS) EPS panel,
389 as defined by EOTA-ETAG 004 [66]. This solution was chosen for its current national widespread
390 use in the energy improvement of buildings [9], [67], [68].

391 **2.6.2. Temperature set**

392 a) CTE

393 The set temperature described in Table 2 was used.

394 **b) Alternative**

395 The set temperature described in Table 3 was used.

396 **2.6.3. Climate**

397 **a) Present**

398 This scenario, based on the present weather situation, was represented by the standard year
399 defined in the document *Spanish Weather for Energy Calculations* (EPW format- SWEC).

400 **b) Future assuming climate change**

401 A weather profile for the year 2050 was created to assess the behaviour of the building stock
402 exposed to climate change, based on HadCM3 and A2 emission conditions.

403 **2.6.4. Combined scenarios**

404 The comparison of different energy models is especially interesting, based on those derived
405 from the monitoring of protocols proposed in national standards, seeking alternatives
406 resembling this behaviour more closely and proposing alternatives for aspects where the biggest
407 differences have been detected (for example, use of heating). Occupant actions affecting
408 envelope performance were modelled following the National Energy Labelling procedure
409 [38]:The use of blinds and solar devices in summer was emulated in the models, considering that
410 in warm periods the aperture level of windows is reduced by 33% as a result of outer blinds -
411 the most frequent - [69], [70], in keeping with the findings of research on solar shading carried
412 out in the area [71].The impact of window aperture was standardised according to this
413 procedure, assuming that windows remain closed during winter, with very short and barely
414 noticeable operation, and in warm periods during the hours in the middle of the day, also with
415 a very short ventilation period. During late evening and night-time hours complete window
416 aperture is expected. This natural ventilation action, with a mean of 4 ACH [69], is within the
417 range identified for the area in the literature [72]–[74]. Although these values can vary greatly
418 and depend on the climate conditions at each point, this study aims to represent the common
419 values of the housing stock in order to ensure the suitable comparison of the complex based on
420 individual behaviour.

421 The modelling incorporates the effect of the presence of neighbouring buildings and its impact
422 on the solar horizon of the model for the different orientations and façades and roofs surfaces.
423 As these buildings are within an urban layout this aspect is crucial to ascertaining the real
424 performance of the building and its enclosures as well as its correlation to solar radiation. The
425 main effect occurs in winter (given the lower solar trajectory), where obstructions prevent solar
426 gains from entering through windows or being stored in walls, while in the summer greater
427 protection is provided to the roofs (in the case of lower buildings) and façades, especially those
428 with SW-NW and NE-SE orientation. This allows the model to closely simulate the real conditions
429 of use and to assess the different urban layouts.

430 **3. Results and discussion**

431 This section discusses and analyses the findings for the energy models of the individual scenarios
432 defined. The data were normalised for inter-model comparison, using the parameter of the
433 building's environmentally controlled gross floor area (routinely applied in residential energy
434 labelling and standard compliance). The energy performance indicators (EnPIs) defined were
435 total thermal energy demand (TD) and cooling (CD)/heating demand (HD) per year.

436 **3.1. Energy demand per model**

437 The behaviour of the different models was studied through the comparison and evolution of the
438 different variables —heating, cooling and yearly total demand for individual building models—
439 in each of the scenarios introduced in order to analyse the degree of response and variation of
440 each of these models. Each building model was represented based on the average energy
441 demand of all the housing units within, comparing the mean value for each scenario (intra-
442 scenario analysis) and between scenarios (inter-scenario analysis), as well as the use of lineal
443 and multiple regression analyses to identify the influence of parameters when needed.
444 Multivariate visualisation is used for pattern recognition.

445 Z-score was used to apply standardised demand result values in order to compare the
446 behaviours of each of the models included below each set of conditions (with very different
447 demand values in each case). , The difference between the result and the sample mean of the
448 set analysed was established and expressed in standard separation deviations (σ). Thanks to this
449 adjustment the models with the most extreme behaviours in each of the parameters analysed
450 (demands) are identified. In general, no models with extreme behaviours (outliers $>3\sigma$) were
451 identified and the different models are within the range of $\pm 1.96\sigma$ in most situations. These
452 values have been represented with a multivariate Star Plot [75] (Figure 4), which is most useful
453 when the scales are comparable. Each ray represents individual study variables (in this case
454 upper vertex: annual demand; lower left vertex: cooling demand; lower right vertex: heating
455 demand).

456 In the original scenario (OA) (Figure 4a) annual energy forecasting performance varies by up to
457 1.5 times within the group. There is some relation between figures and age, with higher demand
458 in older buildings and lower demand in more modern ones (an R-square value of 62.3915% and
459 a correlation factor of 0.789883 show a moderately strong relationship between the variables
460 —p value: 0.0008—). Nonetheless, some of the older buildings have demand figures close to the
461 sample mean (D type), while some modern examples show higher results (model L). It should be
462 noted that the M and N building types date from the final period when insulation was introduced
463 into the construction and, despite the minimal energy-demand sample-minimum values, total
464 figures are very similar to those in non-insulated buildings of a similar age. The building with the
465 highest annual energy demand (A) had mass single-wythe construction, while the non-insulated
466 building with the lowest demand (J) had ceramic brick cavity-walls. However, this does not
467 appear to be a determining factor, since demand in the same sample buildings with ceramic
468 brick single-layer construction shows figures around central values.

469 In this initial scenario for the heating needs the correlation between the most demanding and
470 least demanding models is over double the energy (excluding insulated models), where model
471 E (building with single-wythe enclosures) displays the highest demand compared to L and F (both
472 also have single-wythe enclosures). Given that in this instance all three types had single-wythe
473 façades, the difference is due mostly to a combination of morphological and boundary factors
474 rather than to the specific construction system alone. In this case the different behaviours are
475 probably the result of the joint intervention of additional factors, rather than of the sole
476 influence of the constructive system. In this instance the most influential factors are the
477 aperture of the dwellings and solar obstruction, with the lowest demands found in the buildings
478 with a higher solar capture (orientation, aperture degree and no obstructions).. In heating
479 demand insulated buildings M and N display the highest difference in relation to the sample
480 group. Excluding models with thermal insulation which alters behaviour in some way, regression
481 model analysis establishes that the best explanation for the sample corresponds to the variables
482 linked to the envelope, especially global transmittance and the ratio of envelope per square
483 metre (with the lower Mallows Cp of 3.9692 and a r-square: 58.5182). However, variability is
484 very high as most variables show major correlations and most importantly, this is in keeping with
485 the high intensity of use and prolonged heating periods for this scenario.

486 Cooling behaviour in this scenario was almost a mirror image of heating performance, as the
487 models with the lowest heating demand exhibit the highest cooling demand. The same occurs
488 with variability, with the maximum value almost doubling the minimum. The best annual overall
489 performance was found for model I - with mean heating values and low cooling demand figures
490 for a fabric of single layer concrete-block walls and a rather high wall U-value ($2.17 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$)-
491 which appeared to strike the best balance. Figures for this building type are extremely low, with
492 a z-score of -2σ . This performance can be associated with the presence of continuous balconies
493 across the entire façade, providing horizontal solar protection thus regulating solar capture in
494 winter and preventing it in summer, as a result of orientation and morphology rather than
495 specific wall solutions. Attention should be drawn to the relative high cooling demand in
496 buildings with originally insulated façades (models M and N) compared to non-insulated
497 buildings with a similar configuration (J and K). Insulation during warm periods has limited effect
498 when the morphology is not optimal.

499 In the present weather alternative low-energy intensity scenario (OB) (Figure 4c) types with
500 insulated façades (M and N) show greater differences compared to the sample as opposed to
501 scenario OA, with much lower yearly energy demands. Without this specific type of buildings,
502 demand differentials display similar relative values to those of the OA scenario (around one and
503 a half times higher), although absolute values are lower (50% less). Building performance
504 distribution reflects that from OA, albeit with some differences. In scenario OB the highest total
505 demands are again found in models A and E (close to model D), while models F to H and L
506 represent central values, and the minimum is for I to K types —excluding fabric-insulated M and
507 N. Parameters such as U global and U wall, connected with envelope thermal resistance, are less
508 noticeable in this scenario (linear regression models have no significance over annual energy-
509 demand with p-values over 0.05 in both cases). The seasonal patterns show similar relative-
510 profiles although heating requirements are around 30% lower and 40% for cooling.

511 From the above it is deduced that in an alternative energy-use laxer profile the energy demand
512 profile is moderate in buildings with dense, single-layer fabrics in which the effects of other
513 strategies such as solar control and thermal storage and buffering carry greater weight. The
514 buildings with cavity walls and lower envelope thermal mass were less sensitive to this change
515 of scenario (in relative values). In general there is less scattering of extreme values in
516 distribution. This suggests an important correlation with intermittent use - change in use
517 patterns - which is detrimental to buildings with lower thermal accumulation capacity and a
518 greater exposed surface, provoking the opposite effect in more compact cases with higher
519 thermal masses.

520 Following retrofitting (scenario RA) (Figure 4b), as expected, total demand declined significantly
521 with a roughly homogeneous façade thermal resistance for all types (thermal resistance
522 converges between 0.50 and 0.57 W/m²K due to the addition of insulation), with a substantial
523 reduction in the effect of heating and an increase in the relative weight of cooling in the annual
524 figures. Demand distribution also varied, with a change in the clustering identified in the two
525 preceding scenarios. Somewhat extreme figures were found in type C for annual demand (2.1 σ)
526 and in L-Type for cooling (2.2 σ). The lesser impact of façades heightened that of other
527 parameters such as the roof or WWR. Under an alternative indoor control pattern (RB) (Figure
528 4d) demand is lowered substantially, particularly for cooling, following much the same pattern
529 as that observed in scenarios OA and OB. As in scenario RA, the highest total and heating
530 demands were associated with model C, although the absolute values are 20% lower. The
531 combination of low (but not the lowest) fabric thermal resistance, low WWR and small housing
532 unit size makes this type of building highly sensitive to envelope losses.

533 Scenarios RA and RB (Figures 4b and 4d) show similar distribution of means for the models with
534 attenuated values related to OA and OB. However, as they are clearly differentiated sample sets,
535 specific distributions show major changes in the behaviour of the scenario (Kolmogorov-Smirnov
536 tests show a statistically significant difference between both distributions with a level of trust of
537 95.0% and a DN-value of 0.7857 and 0.7142 and p-value of 0.000352 and 0.0015 for OA-RA and
538 OB-RB respectively). The differences between maximum and minimum were mostly attenuated
539 in RB with respect to RA, as is the case in the original scenarios (OA and OB).

540 When climate change was assumed in the scenarios, heating accounted for far less of the total
541 demand (23% for the mean values) than cooling.

542 Comparing both climate situations, it is worth highlighting the significant reduction in heating
543 and increase in cooling for future forecast. There is also a reduction in efficiency of insulation
544 measures between the original envelope and the improved one in scenario FOB/FRB. The B
545 scenario was selected for its closer representation of the operation of actual buildings, and
546 consequently greater capacity for evaluating the potential for energy change among the
547 different scenarios.

548 In the future scenario with buildings in original conditions the effect of heating is far less
549 noticeable in the overall requirements (23% of total mean values), whereas behaviour in cooling
550 conditions is far more significant. The lowest total demand is observed in the insulated buildings
551 (models M and N), albeit with very similar values to those of non-insulated buildings I and J,

552 which show the lowest demand in the group without insulation. Models M and N present
553 medium cooling demand, with low total values due to the reduced heating demand resulting
554 from the façade insulation. However, this does not appear to be particularly effective for heating
555 demand control. In contrast, the demand values for the most balanced non-insulated models
556 within the sample (I and J) are slightly higher (close to the mean), in keeping with an envelope
557 without insulation. Nevertheless, their morphology benefits cooling control. Model E displays
558 the highest heating demand, with behaviour in keeping with prior analyses. However, models A,
559 C and D also present high heating demand values, which can be linked to a lower thermal
560 resistance of these enclosures compared to the rest of the group. Although heating demand
561 values are relatively low compared to the current scenarios (with a 35% reduction between
562 scenarios), maximum and minimum values vary greatly, exceeding double the value without
563 taking into account freestanding buildings. There is a high incidence of the parameter associated
564 to the thermal resistance of façades (U-value) in the distribution of heating demand values,
565 albeit with great variations (linear correlation r-square: 46.2407% indicates a moderately strong
566 relationship between variables with a standard deviation of the residuals of 2.4105 with p-value
567 of 0.0075). Variability is reduced in the case of cooling, with an approximate minimum-maximum
568 ratio of 1.6, despite the much higher absolute values and the significant increase when
569 compared to the current situation, doubling the mean cooling demand of scenario OA, although
570 in this case there are no predominant parameters in the distribution process and B-type and I-
571 Type are found in extreme positions, with z-scores over +/-2 (2.1; -2.1)

572 For the situation of future climate (2050) and improved envelope, - and ahead of M and N, which
573 could be considered to have excessive insulation - models I and J display the lowest total energy
574 demand and jointly the lowest cooling demand. Heating demand is also reduced in both cases.
575 Models C and F display the highest total energy demand, with the highest cooling demand also
576 observed in model F. The features noted above are confirmed as the poor behaviour of model
577 C cannot be linked to the thermal resistance of its enclosures —wall R-value— (in this case with
578 equal values throughout the sample) or Global transmittance value, with no actual correlations
579 as R-square only reaches 12.2233% for FOB and a very low 0.8720 % for FRB both with p-value
580 over 0.005 (0.22 and 0.7508). This model also shows the highest heating demand, followed by
581 model E. Although the maximum overall value of model F is also due to its high cooling demand,
582 it presents one of the lowest heating demands in the group. This can be attributed to high solar
583 radiation capture throughout the year (high ratio of openings to surface area and effect of the
584 roof), which allows control of the need for heating but is especially problematic in the warm
585 period, despite the presence of insulation.

586 When observing the symmetry and scope of the behaviour in relation to the group mean (Figure
587 4) in general the models displaying the most balanced behaviour and lowest demands are J and
588 N, whereas models C, F and L show the least balance and the highest demands.

589

590 *Figure 4: Mean total, heating and cooling demands for each model in the sample and star plot*
 591 *multivariate visualisation of model energy demands under six scenarios (bar graph:*
 592 *blue=cooling demand; red=heating demand; green=total demand; Chambers graph: top*
 593 *vertex=yearly demand; lower left vertex=cooling demand; lower right vertex=heating demand)*

594

595

3.2. General energy demands for the sample studied: inter-scenario comparison

596

597

Partial and total energy demands are shown in Figure 5, comparing the results for the six scenarios: present, retrofitted and for the year 2050 assuming climate change, each with and without retrofitting. The average values for all the scenarios and the differentials between the non-retrofitted and retrofitted versions in each group (expressed in relative and absolute values) are listed in Figure 6 for heating and in Figure 7 for cooling demand.

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Figure 5: Mean HVAC energy demand (kWh/m²) in six scenarios.

Figure 6: Comparison of average heating demand (kWh/m²) for all models by scenario (left: relative variation (%) with and without retrofitting; right: absolute variation (kWh/m²) with and without retrofitting)

	A			B			FB				A			B			FB		
O	21.6	-36.57%	13.7	101.46%	27.6		21.6	-7.9	13.7	13.9	27.6								
	-18.52%		-16.79%		-14.13%		-4		-2.3		-3.9								
R	17.6	-35.23%	11.4	107.89%	23.7		17.6	-6.2	11.4	12.3	23.7								

Figure 7: Comparison of average cooling demand (kWh/m²) for all models by scenario (left: relative variation (%) with and without retrofitting; right: absolute variation in kWh/m² with and without retrofitting).

Where:

- A Spanish standard set temperature
- B alternative set temperature
- O original
- R retrofitted
- F Future climate.
- HD Heating demand (kWh/m²)
- CD Cooling demand (kWh/m²)
- TD Total demand (kWh/m²)

604 A comparison of the type O (original) scenarios showed the significant effect of the intensity of
 605 use of HVAC systems and the adoption of different set-points. The implementation of an
 606 alternative schedule, closer to common practice, and the strict application of the analysis to the
 607 areas of housing units that are currently conditioned (OB) lowered yearly demand to
 608 approximately 70 % of the initial value (OA).

609 The distribution of seasonal demand also varied. In scenario B heating and cooling tended to be
 610 more balanced (heating: 47.7% / cooling: 52.3%), whereas cooling carried greater weight in
 611 scenario A (heating: 42.4% / cooling: 57.6%). A seasonal analysis showed that modifying the
 612 indoor conditions greatly affected summer values, as the heating demand from OA to OB
 613 decreased by 21.4%, compared to a 36.6% reduction in cooling.

614 Type R scenarios reflected the effect of improving the vertical opaque envelope (façade
 615 enclosures) through energy retrofitting. Improving thermal insulation lowered yearly demand in
 616 both cases (RA, RB), although the reduction was more noticeable in the lower intensity scenario
 617 than in the higher one: RB=33.2%; RA=29.9%. Lower demand was observed primarily in winter,
 618 with a greater decrease in heating (RA: 45.9%; RB: 51.2%) than in cooling demand (RA: 18.5%;
 619 RB: 16.8%) as a result of façade insulation. As stated, façade improvements greatly impacted
 620 heating, reducing the energy needs to around half the initial requirement. Although demand for
 621 cooling was also reduced, this decrease was less than one-fifth of the initial value.

622 The climate change (CC) scenarios assumed an intensity use of type B or lower, considered to
 623 best represent the predominant conditions in this housing stock. The assessment for the year
 624 2050 indicated a significant change in energy performance, even under moderate use. In the
 625 future scenario, climate change with higher mean temperatures and longer summers made the
 626 winters much less severe, thereby raising the weight of summer time demand in the total. The

627 net result was a considerable reduction in heating demand, even with the original envelopes,
628 with an equally considerable rise in cooling demand, even under less strict summertime
629 temperature targets (compared to current standards for premises with mechanical HVAC
630 systems).

631 In the future scenario, façade improvements (FRB) improved the control of yearly demand,
632 reduced by 23.3%, attenuating the effects of CC and delivering yearly values similar to those
633 recorded for the original situation (OB). However, this effect was not balanced as the relative
634 weights of seasonal performance were highly impacted and both scenarios (OB and FRB) were
635 rendered unsuitable for comparison. In FRB, cooling (86%) clearly prevailed over heating
636 (13.4%).

637 In this scenario, heating demand was marginal, dipping to values below half those of the
638 scenario without façade improvements (FOB) and to less than one-third of the current values
639 assuming low intensity use (OB). These observations reinforce the idea that thermal resistance
640 of the enclosure is a primary factor in preventing energy loss. In contrast, the difference in
641 present and future cooling demand assuming CC is under 15%.

642 While the relative values would appear to indicate much more significant reductions in heating
643 than in cooling demand, the absolute values revealed a more balanced situation. Insulating the
644 façade lowered heating demand by 54.9% and cooling demand by just 14.1%, whereas the
645 overall reduction was actually 4.5 kWh/m² for heating and 3.9 kWh/m² for cooling. This can be
646 explained by the relatively low heating and high cooling demand in this scenario. The
647 differentials in absolute terms given in Table 7 show that façade insulation had a greater effect
648 on heating; the greater the indoor-outdoor temperature difference, the higher the impact. The
649 same pattern was observed in connection with the overall reduction in cooling demand between
650 FOB and FRB, compared to the more moderate findings for OB and RB.

651 **3.3. Application to general stock models**

652 After analysing the variability and dispersion of energy demand for each regime under the
653 different study scenarios (Annex 1) together with the density traces, behavioural models can be
654 established to represent the population, providing an image of possible evolution under the
655 different scenarios of the set of residential buildings.

656 Therefore, the proposed models should be applied to the information of the entire housing
657 stock, returning to previous analyses for the study of specific cases, or to behaviour groups to
658 avoid possible deviation of the data when modifying the scale.

659 Distribution models were selected for the best fit. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov non-parametric test
660 was applied to verify the fit to the proposed distributions, with the best fit within 70.11% of the
661 population (95% significance) and non-rejection of the null-hypothesis (K-S p-value>0.05). The
662 results and complementary tests are shown in Annex 2.

663 Analysis of the data obtained allows representative probabilistic distributions to be incorporated
664 in order to forecast a performance model to be exported to the general case set, providing a

665 general prediction model based on probability (assuming the approximation). Normal
666 distribution or related types of distribution (i.e. inverse Gaussian) were selected to ensure better
667 applicability and commonality. The prediction models of the annual energy demand for thermal
668 conditioning of the OB, RA, R and FOB scenarios can be adjusted to a normal probabilistic
669 distribution. At the same time, the OA and FRB scenarios are better represented by an inverse
670 Gaussian distribution (Figure 8). Table 7 shows the defining statistical parameters of the
671 different distributions.

672

673 Figure 8: Probability distribution for overall energy demand per unit of gross floor area (kWh/m²)
674 in six scenarios. OA: Red; OB: Blue; RA: dot-Orange; RB: dot-Cyan; FOB: Green; FRB: dot-green

675

Table 7. Statistical parameters for the distributions in Figure 8.

Scenario	Mode	Scale	Tolerance intervals	
			Upper limit (kWh/m ²)	Lower limit (kWh/m ²)
OA	34.67	4.92	49.01	29.00
FRB	27.48	41.2	24.88	12.52
	27.4643	41.0988	34.8	21.2
Scenario	Mean	Standard deviation	Tolerance intervals	
			Upper limit (kWh/m ²)	Lower limit (kWh/m ²)
OB	26.22	4.7	47.8693	4.6020
RA	26.25	4.93	49.01	3.42
RB	17.48	3.57	33.92	1.03
FOB	35.88	4.42	33.17	18.98

676

677 The results obtained are in keeping with other research, which establishes that total energy
678 needs in mild and warm zones will increase despite the significant reduction in the influence of
679 the heating. This is the case of the USA [30], mild Australian climate zones [76], and especially

680 Mediterranean areas such as Greece, with a significant reduction in heating needs and a
681 substantial increase in cooling demands [31]. Mild zones may be the most sensitive to change,
682 given the predominance of lower performance buildings, as has also been pointed out by [76]
683 and [77] in relation to social housing in Brazil.

684 **4. Conclusions**

685 The collection of stock-representative samples did not exhibit uniform performance values, as
686 was expected. The distribution was characterised by a wide base with broad scattering and
687 around 50% differences between maximum and minimum values for most of the scenarios.
688 Although many of the models share construction definitions (particularly in façades), the
689 forecast values were not clustered or directly associated with such factors. In fact, demand was
690 the result of the combined effect of the many complex factors defining each model.

691 Strategies based on the improvement of the envelope insulation, particularly its opaque
692 components, improve building-stock performance. This is mainly noticed during cold periods,
693 providing the occupants practise thermal control close to the standards, which currently differ
694 from real behaviour. This effect weakens as the climate evolves.

695 The choice of the energy intensity model plays a fundamental role in predicting the performance
696 of improvement measures. When more realistic indoor control schemes and reliable set-points
697 are used, the energy saving potential of the insulation-based actions is noticeably reduced,
698 decreasing the actual weight of winter in the energy balance, especially in the case of future
699 scenarios. Façade improvements were less effective in reducing consumption in scenarios
700 characterised by lower energy-intensity with fewer temperature requirements or considering
701 future climate change actions (where the cold season is not as influential). In these cases,
702 although the decrease observed was proportionally significant (around 50% for heating demand
703 in the scenarios analysed), the absolute figures were less so. These results directly impact the
704 cost-effectiveness of intervention.

705 Retrofitting by adding thermal insulation to the envelope had less impact on cooling demand,
706 which decreased by less than 20% in these scenarios. The impact of this insulation was less
707 noticeable in the future climate change scenario than in the current one. The reduction in
708 demand was lower, decreasing from over 30% to under 24%, while the absolute values were
709 particularly small in the current scenario and distribution was inverted: the decrease was lower
710 in winter than in summer. Nevertheless, we should bear in mind that heating demands are more
711 likely to translate into actual energy consumption, primarily because dwellings are occupied for
712 more hours in winter than in summer, so that the analysis of heating demands should not be
713 ruled out.

714 Although the effect of climate change on the area is quite mild in comparison to other European
715 locations [21], [31], [78], [79], this process shows the potential disruption to the energy
716 performance of the oldest housing stock. There is a need for a transition towards a building
717 energy performance model that is less dependent on the thermal resistance of the envelope
718 and thus more dependent on the building type and solar radiation management. The expected

719 rise of the cooling demand (with higher loads and longer warm periods), along with shorter
720 periods with heating needs will result in a change of the energy profile of the buildings, possibly
721 leading in turn to a significant increase in the annual demand compared with the current
722 situation (around 50%). This demand will result in real consumption depending on the evolution
723 of the use of Air Conditioning in residential buildings and the situation of energy poverty of the
724 population, despite the significant impact foreseen.

725 Although heating total loads will decrease in this climate process they will still be present, and
726 the comfort and health of inhabitants will be a driving force (due both to exposure time and to
727 the presence of anomalous climate periods such as extreme weather episodes). It should be
728 remembered that this performance does not have a homogeneous distribution but rather
729 displays scattered behaviour. Therefore, the stock includes buildings with high heating demands
730 even under warm scenarios (commonly buildings associated with lower income population
731 where energy poverty usually occurs).

732 Under future climate change scenarios, incident solar radiation energy-gains would increase
733 their year-round effect due to increased surface irradiation. The longer warm seasons will
734 increase the contribution of façades to the capture of radiation energy, thus widening the gap
735 between buildings that are properly oriented and those that are not. Roofs will become a key
736 envelope element, especially in buildings with a higher roof to gross floor-area ratio (low rise
737 collective homes) unlike the usual situation of the current stock, where the roof envelope is less
738 important in the overall demand of the entire building. Therefore, roofs should be a major focus
739 for improvement actions.

740 However, there is a key factor in energy performance which cannot be modified for existing
741 stock layout, as it is inherent in its construction. The solar orientation and the sun blockades of
742 the buildings and their surroundings will play an increasing role in energy demand values, with
743 buildings with similar features presenting higher divergences depending on boundary
744 conditions.

745 While the building type and boundary factors of built heritage cannot easily be modified, these
746 can be used as design rules for future development in the region, both in terms of city planning
747 and future construction. The key role of the orientation and proper design of the surroundings
748 in the future Mediterranean city should be understood and tackled.

749 The most balanced performances (annual figures) —under all scenarios— are found in medium
750 to high- rise buildings with façades with multiple orientations and limited vertical solar
751 obstructions. Suitable performances are also found in buildings with two predominant façades
752 (mainly NW-SE orientations) but with good solar protection, displaying low cooling demands at
753 the expense of higher heating needs. Buildings with SW-NE orientation are the most common
754 and usually present overall mean performances which vary in accordance with their degree of
755 solar obstruction. In contrast, façades with E-W orientation are the least favourable for both
756 types of demand, with higher impact in low-rise buildings.

757

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955 **Annex 1**

956 Table A1.1. Statistical summary of heating energy demands in six scenarios

Scenario	Mean	Standard deviation	CV	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Standard bias	Standardised kurtosis
OA	15.91	6.16	38.7%	6.72	25.45	18.73	0.097	-0.849
OB	12.53	4.44	35.4%	5.2	19.7	14.5	-0.081	-0.722
RA	8.62	4.33	50.2%	3.62	15.67	12.05	0.717	-1.014
RB	6.08	3.65	60.1%	2.08	12.45	10.37	0.902	-0.811
FOB	8.24	3.15	38.3%	3.06	13.18	10.12	-0.006	-0.760
FRB	3.74	2.13	57.0%	1.61	7.86	6.25	1.356	-0.436
Total	9.19	5.71	62.2%	1.61	25.45	23.84	3.011	0.278

957

958 Table A1.2: Statistical summary of cooling energy demands in six scenarios

Scenario	Mean	Standard deviation	CV	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Standard bias	Standardised kurtosis
OA	21.60	4.29	19.8%	13.17	29.22	16.05	-0.575	-0.120
OB	13.68	2.43	17.7%	8.53	17.76	9.23	-0.766	0.257
RA	17.63	4.03	22.8%	11.15	26.11	14.96	0.448	0.155
RB	11.39	2.81	24.7%	6.91	16.06	9.15	0.015	-0.182
FOB	27.64	3.27	11.8%	20.98	34.68	13.70	0.256	0.938
FRB	23.74	4.26	17.9%	17.77	32.60	14.83	1.204	0.147
Total	19.28	6.66	34.5%	6.91	34.68	27.77	0.667	-1.617

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960

961 Table A1.3: Statistical summary of total energy demands in six scenarios

Scenario	Mean	Standard deviation	CV	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Standard bias	Standardised kurtosis
OA	37.52	6.27	16.7%	29.02	49.06	20.04	0.680	-0.701
OB	26.22	4.70	17.9%	18.98	33.17	14.19	-0.034	-0.823
RA	26.26	4.96	18.9%	19.67	37.32	17.65	0.962	0.232
RB	17.47	3.56	20.4%	12.52	24.88	12.36	0.686	-0.242
FOB	35.88	4.42	12.3%	29.66	44.37	14.71	0.078	-0.376
FRB	27.48	4.41	16.0%	21.23	34.84	13.61	0.396	-0.679
Total	28.47	8.18	28.7%	12.52	49.06	36.54	0.752	-0.753

962

963

964 **Annex 2**

965 The distribution characteristics for each case were defined based on their parameters. The Test
966 battery panel performs different approaches designed to determine if the data could reasonably
967 come from the selected distribution or not (most on the case of normality). For each test the
968 hypotheses are:

- 969 • Null hypothesis: the data are independent samples of a normal distribution
- 970 • Hypothesis Alt .: the data are not independent samples of a normal distribution

971 Since the smallest P-value of all the tests performed is greater than or equal to 0.05, the selected
972 distribution cannot be rejected with 95% confidence.

973 The tolerance interval for each distribution was provided, with 95% confidence, and the
974 certainty that at least 70.11% of the population is included (Table 7).

975 Table A2.1. Statistical summary of models in six scenarios

Distribution		Mean	STD	Scale	
OA	Inverse Gaussian	37.528		39.1797	
OB	Normal	26.2357	4.700		
RA	Normal	26.2571	4.96072		
RB	Normal	17.4786	3.5732		
FOB	Normal	35.8929	4.43577		
FRB	Inverse Gaussian	27.4643		41.0988	
Chi-square	Chi-square	G.1.	p-value	>0.05 (95%)	
OA	2.3710	2	0.3055		
OB	0.77965	2	0.6775		
RA	0.8450	1	0.3579		
RB	1.5786	1	0.2089		
FOB	2.49434	1	0.1142		
FRB	2.23574	2	0.3269		
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	D+	D-	DN	p-value	>0.05 (95%)
OA	0.18366	0.09111	0.18366	0.7324	
OB	0.104798	0.135352	0.135352	0.9596	
RA	0.101252	0.0931152	0.101252	0.9987	
RB	0.16268	0.1231	0.16268	0.8525	
FOB	0.16485	0.16148	0.16485	0.8412	
FRB	0.08639	0.10684	0.10684	0.9972	
Anderson-Darling	A ²	Mod. form	p-value	>0.05 (95%)	
OA	0.338383	0.338383	>=0.10		
OB	0.264951	0.282186	0.637368		
RA	0.2188	0.23312	0.7978		
RB	0.3314	0.3529	0.4655		
FOB	0.452514	0.4819	0.2310		
FRB	0.20117	0.20117	>=0.10		

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